

SUBADDITIVE MEASURE ON JORDAN ALGEBRAS

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Annotation

This article proves that the topological Jordan algebra of measurable elements with respect to sub additive measure is an OJ - algebra .

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Let $\mathbf{A}$ be a finite JBW algebra, τ be an exact normal finite trace on $\mathbf{A}$. Let m be a subadditive measure on $\mathbf{A}$. From the results [2-3] it follows that m can be represented as $m(x) = \gamma(\tau(x))$. Let N be the space of normal functionals on $\mathbf{A}$.

Lemma 1. Set
$$S = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} \{g \in N : -nm \leq g \leq nm \text{ на } \nabla\}$$

is dense in the Banach space N , where $g \leq nm$ on ∇ means that $g(e) \leq nm(e)$ for any $e \in \nabla$.

Proof . If S is not dense in N , then there exists a continuous linear functional x_0 on N such that $x_0 \neq 0$. $g(x_0) = 0$ for everyone $g \in S$. Since it is $g(x_0) = 0$ equivalent to the equality $g(r(x_0)) = 0$, where $r(x_0)$ is the support of the element x_0 , it suffices to prove that $r(x_0) = 0$. It is easy to see that $\tau \leq m$ on ∇ . The functional $\tau_e(x) = \tau(ex)$ also belongs to the set S . By assumption $g(r(x_0)) = 0$, for any $g \in S$ and in particular $\tau_e(r(x_0)) = 0$, $\forall e \in \nabla$. Letting $e = r(x_0)$ we have that $\tau(r(x_0)) = 0$. Due to accuracy, we τ conclude that $r(x_0) = 0$. This means that $x_0 = 0$. Therefore, $x_0 = 0$. The lemma is proven.

Let $\mathbf{A}$ - JBW - algebra, ∇ be the set of idempotents of $\mathbf{A}$. m is a finite subadditive measure on $\mathbf{A}$, t is the topology of convergence in measure m .

Theorem 1. If the sequence of elements $\{x_n\} \subset \mathbf{A}$ $t - c$ tends to zero and is bounded on the norm ($\|x_n\| \leq 1, n = 1, 2, \dots$), then it $*$ - weakly converges to zero in $\mathbf{A}$.

Proof. Let $x_n \xrightarrow{t} x$ i.e. for any $\varepsilon, \delta > 0$ there is a number n_0 such that $x_n \in N(\varepsilon, \delta)$ for $n \geq n_0$. This means that there is a sequence $\{e_n\} \subset \nabla$ such that $m(e_n^\perp) \leq \delta$, $\|U_{e_n} x_n\| \leq \varepsilon$, $n \geq n_0$.

It needs to be shown that $x_0 \rightarrow \theta$ *- weakly, i.e. $g(x_n) \rightarrow 0$ for any normal state $g \in N$. Let first $g \in S$, i.e. $g(e_n^\perp) \leq k_0 m(e_n^\perp)$ for some natural k_0 . We have:

$$g(x_n) = g(U_{e_n} x_n) + 2g(U_{e_n, 1-e_n} x_n) + (U_{1-e_n} x_n)$$

and $|g(U_{e_n} x_n)| \leq \|U_{e_n} x_n\| g(1) \leq \varepsilon$. Let us estimate the second term. Because

$U_{e_n, 1-e_n} x_n = 2(1-e_n)(e_n x_n)$, then due to the Schwartz inequality

$$\begin{aligned} |g(U_{e_n, 1-e_n} x_n)| &\leq 2\sqrt{g(e^\perp)g((e_n x_n)^2)} \leq \\ &\leq 2\sqrt{g(e^\perp)} \sqrt{\|e_n x_n\|^2} \leq 2\sqrt{k_0 m(e^\perp)} \|x_n\| \leq 2\sqrt{k_0} \sqrt{\delta}. \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account the equality $U_{1-e_n} x_n = (1-e_n)(x_n - 2e_n x_n)$, it similarly turns out that

$$|g(U_{1-e_n} x_n)| \leq 3\sqrt{k_0} \sqrt{\delta}. \text{ By virtue of arbitrariness, } \varepsilon, \delta \text{ this implies that } g(x_n) \rightarrow 0.$$

Let now $f \in N$ be an arbitrary normal state. By Lemma 1, for any $\eta > 0$ there exists $g \in S$ such that $\|f - g\| \leq \eta$. Then if $g(e) \leq k_0 m(e)$, then for $n \geq n_0$ we have:

$$\begin{aligned} |f(x_n)| &\leq |(f - g)(x_n)| + |f(x_n)| \leq \|f - g\| \|x_n\| + |g(x_n)| \leq \eta + \varepsilon + 7\sqrt{k_0} \sqrt{\delta}, \text{ i.e.} \\ |f(x_n)| &\rightarrow 0. \text{ So, it } x_n \rightarrow 0 \text{ *- weakly. The theorem has been proven.} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2. The algebra $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ is a universal *OJ*-algebra, the set of bounded elements of which coincides with $\mathbf{A}$.

Proof. In terms of continuity in the topology t of the operation of multiplication in $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, the set of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^+$ all squares of elements from $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ is the t -closure of the cone $\mathbf{A}^+ = \{a^2, a \in \mathbf{A}\}$ JBW are algebras $\mathbf{A}$. The cone $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^+$ defines a $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ partial order, which obviously satisfies axioms 1), 2), 4) of the definition of a partial order and induces the initial partial order on $\mathbf{A}$.

The proof of the second part of the theorem (i.e., the set of bounded elements of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ which coincides with $\mathbf{A}$) is carried out similarly to the proof of the theorem from [1].

Let be $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_0$ an arbitrary maximal strongly associative subalgebra $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$. Due to t being the continuity of multiplication in $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, subalgebra $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_0$ closed. Let $K = \{a \in \hat{\mathbf{A}}_0, a \geq 0\}$. The set of elements of the form $(1+x)^{-1}$, $x \in K$, is contained, as noted earlier, in $\mathbf{A}$. Since all are $x \in \hat{\mathbf{A}}_0$ compatible, then by Lemma 1.3.2 from [1] the family is $\{(1+x)^{-1}, x \in K\}$ compatible. Let $\mathbf{A}_0$ be a maximal strongly associative subalgebra $\mathbf{A}$ containing this family. By

virtue of the corollary of Theorem 1.2.2 . in [1], $\mathbf{A}_0$ is a topological semifield. If $\bar{A}_0$ the closure $\mathbf{A}_0$ in $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, then due to completeness $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_0$ is a complete topological semifield and hence a universal semifield . Obviously, it is $\bar{A}_0$ strongly associative in $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$. Let's show that $\bar{A}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{A}}_0$. Since $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_0$, it suffices to check that $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_0 \subset \bar{A}_0$.

Let $x \in K$, then $(1+x)^{-1} \in \mathbf{A}_0$ by definition $\mathbf{A}_0$. The carrier $r(z)$ of the element $z = (1+x)^{-1}$ is equal to one. Indeed,

$$z^2(1-r(z)) = U_z(1-r(z)) = 0;$$

applying the operator to this equality $U_{1+x} = U_z^{-1}$, we obtain $1-r(z) = \theta$, i.e. $r(z) = 1$. Since in the universal semifield every element with support equal to one is invertible, then in the semifield $\bar{A}_0$ exists z^{-1} . Due to the uniqueness of the inverse element in the Jordan algebra.

$$(1+x) = z^{-1} \in \bar{A}_0, \text{ i.e. } x \in \bar{A}_0, \text{ i.e. } K \subset \bar{A}_0.$$

For any $x \in \bar{A}_0$ we have

$$x = \frac{1}{2}(1+x)^2 - x^2 - 1 \in K - K - K \subset \bar{A}_0 \text{ those. } \hat{\mathbf{A}}_0 = \bar{A}_0.$$

Thus, we have proved that every maximal strongly associative subalgebra $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ is a universal semifield . In particular, axioms 3) and (II) *OJ* are algebras for $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$.

It remains only to verify the fulfillment of the axiom (I). Let be $\{x_\alpha\}$ an increasing network of elements bounded from above in $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$. We can assume that $\theta \leq x_\alpha \leq x$ for all α . There is $a = (1+x)^{-1} \in \mathbf{A}$. By virtue of the positivity of the operator U_a in $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ and, therefore, in $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, the network is $\{U_a x_\alpha\}$ increasing and bounded from above by the element $U_a x = (1+x)^{-2} x \leq 1$. Therefore, $\{U_a x_\alpha\} \subset \mathbf{A}$ and therefore in $\mathbf{A}$ exists $b = \sup U_a x_\alpha$. Then, obviously, the element $x_0 U_a^{-1} b = U_{1+x} b$ is the least upper bound for $\{x_\alpha\}$.

Let us show that $x_\alpha \rightarrow x_0$ in the topology t . Since $U_a x_\alpha \uparrow b$ in *JBW*- algebra $\mathbf{A}$ and for monotone networks in *JBW* - algebras, the concepts of ordinal, *- weak and strong convergence coincide, then $U_a x_\alpha \rightarrow b$ strongly, i.e. $\rho((U_a x_\alpha - b)^2) \rightarrow 0$ for any normal state ρ . In particular, $\tau((U_a x_\alpha - b)^2) \rightarrow 0$ for any $\varepsilon, \delta_1 > 0$ there exists a_0 such that $\tau((U_a x_\alpha - b)^2) \leq \varepsilon^2 \delta_1$ for $a \geq a_0$. From here, as in the proof of Theorem 1.8.3, it follows that $(U_a x_\alpha - b) \in N(\varepsilon, \delta)$, with respect to the subadditive measure, i.e., $U_a x_\alpha \rightarrow b$ in the topology t . Since multiplication in the Jordan algebra $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$ is continuous in the topology t , then

$$x_a = U_{1+x} U_a x_a \xrightarrow{t} U_{1+x} b = x_0$$

If now $y \in \widehat{\mathbf{A}}$ and $y \leftrightarrow x_a$ for any a , then, due to the continuity of multiplication in $\widehat{\mathbf{A}}$ and the fact that $x_a \xrightarrow{t} x_0$, it follows that $y \leftrightarrow x_0$, which proves the fulfillment of the $\widehat{\mathbf{A}}$ axioms (I) *OJ*-algebras. The theorem has been proven.

It follows from this theorem that in the case of finite *JBW*-algebras *OJ*-algebras of measurable elements constructed from the trace [1] and from finite subadditive measures coincide.

References:

1. Кодиров К., Йигиталиев Й. Топология сходимости по мере на-алгебрах //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 491-495.
2. Кодиров К., Йигиталиев Й. Инновационный метод обучения высшей математике //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 71.
3. Kodirov K. R., Nishonbaev A. S. On the scientific basis of forming students' logical competence //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 3. – С. 123-128.
4. Raximovich K. K. et al. Some Methods for Solving Fourth-Order Equations //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 127-130.
5. Kodirov K. R. et al. COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING SOME ELEMENTS OF MATHEMATICS LESSON DESIGN METHODOLOGY //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 390-394.
6. Кодиров К., Йигиталиев Й. ФИНАНСОВАЯ ГРАМОТНОСТЬ С ЭЛЕМЕНТАРНОЙ МАТЕМАТИКОЙ //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 435-438.
7. Кодиров К., Йигиталиев Й. -ИЗМЕРИМЫЕ ОПЕРАТОРЫ НА-АЛГЕБРАХ //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 485-490.
8. Komiljon K., Yuldoshali Y. Subadditive measure on projectors of von neumann algebra //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 26-28.
9. Komiljon K., Yuldoshali Y., Begzod S. Communication of sab additive measures on Jordan banach algebra //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 29-31.
10. Raximovich, K. K., & Shokirjon o'g'li, T. T. (2022). *OJ-ALGEBRA OF MEASURABLE ELEMENTS WITH RESPECT TO A SUBADDITIVE MEASURE ON JORDAN ALGEBRAS*. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 4, 19-21.
11. Khursanalievich, K. U., Ugli, T. T. S., & Askarali, M. (2022). *DRAWING AND IMAGE MODELS TOOL MATH LEARNING OPTIONS*. American Journal of Applied Science and Technology, 2(09), 26-34.
12. Kodirov, K., Nishonboyev, A., Ruzikov, M., & Tuxtasinov, T. (2022). *SUBADDITIVE MEASURE ON VON NEUMANN ALGEBRAS*. International scientific journal of Biruni, 1(2), 134-139.
13. Кодиров, К. Р., Тухтасинов, Т. Ш., & Йўлдошали, Й. У. (2021). *Связь топологии сходимости по мере на алгебрах Фон Неймана*. Вестник магистратуры, 7.
14. Abdumannopov, M. M., Akhmedov, O. U., & Tokhtasinov, T. (2022). *ESSENTIAL MODES FOR ACTIVATING MASTERING SUBJECTS AT SCHOOLS*. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES, 3(12), 1-4.

15. Nishonboyev, A., Tukhtasinov, T., & Ro'zikov, M. (2023). WAYS TO FORM INDEPENDENT THINKING OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING MATHEMATICS. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(3), 49-51.
16. Рузиков, М. (2022). Уч ўлчовли Лаплас тенгламаси учун ярим чексиз параллелепипедда нолокал чегаравий масала. Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal, 1(5), 128-137.
17. Kodirov, K., Nishonboyev, A., Ruzikov, M., & Alimov, Z. (2022). Formation of students' knowledge and skills in the educational process based on the active approach. International scientific journal of Biruni, 1(2), 339-344.

